

Type 1 Familial Partial Lipodystrophy: Understanding the Köbberling Syndrome

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Abbreviated Title: Köbberling syndrome

Key words: Familial Partial Lipodystrophy, body composition, visceral adipose tissue.

Word count: Abstract: 315, Text: 3616

Number of Figures and Tables: 7

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are indebted to the patients of this study for their collaboration.

This study has been funded by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (grant number: PI081449) and the European Regional Development Fund, FEDER. In addition, SRG was awarded a Research Fellowship, granted by the Asociación Española de Familiares y Afectados de Lipodistrofias (AELIP).

Conflict of interest: The authors have nothing to disclose.

1
2 **ABSTRACT**
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4 **PURPOSE:** Familial partial lipodystrophies (FPLD) are Mendelian disorders involving abnormal
5 body fat distribution and insulin resistance. The current classification includes the Köbberling
6 Syndrome (FPLD1), characterized by fat loss in the lower limbs and abnormal fat accumulation in
7 other areas. FPLD1 appears to be heritable, but little is known about it, including putative contributing
8 mutations. We aimed to characterize this syndrome better by evaluating a group of women with
9 phenotypic features of FPLD1.
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18 **SUBJECTS AND METHODS:** This is a case-controlled study in which 98 women with FPLD1 that
19 lacked classical mutations known to cause FPLD were compared to 60 women without lipodystrophy
20 and 25 patients with type 2 FPLD (Dunnigan disease). Clinical course, body composition by DEXA,
21 HbA1c, lipid profile, insulin, leptin and family history were evaluated in all of participants. **Analyses**
22 **of receiver-operating characteristic (ROC) curve were performed for FPLD1 diagnosis,**
23 **comparing different truncal:limbs ratios.**
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33 **RESULTS:** Among patients with FPLD1, 68% developed recognizable lipodystrophy before
34 adolescence, and most displayed an autosomal dominant pattern (86%). Women with FPLD1 had less
35 lower-limb adipose tissue than women without lipodystrophy, but significantly more than patients
36 with Dunnigan disease. Moreover, metabolic disturbances occurred more frequently in the FPLD1
37 group (81%) than in a non-lipodystrophic group (30%, $p<0.05$). The severity of metabolic
38 disturbances was inversely proportional to the percentage of fat in the lower extremities and directly
39 proportional to the amount of visceral adipose tissue. Metabolic profiles were worse in FPLD1 than in
40 Dunnigan disease. **According to the ROC curve analysis, the best ratio was Subscapular/Calf**
41 **skinfolts (KöB index), with a cut-off value of 3.477 (sensitivity: 89 %; specificity: 84%).**
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54 **CONCLUSIONS:** FPLD1 was an early onset, autosomal dominant lipodystrophy characterized by fat
55 loss in the lower limbs and abnormal fat accumulation in the abdominal visceral region, associated to
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insulin resistance and metabolic disorders. **A KöB index higher than 3.477 is highly suggestive of this syndrome.**

INTRODUCTION

Familial partial lipodystrophy (FPLD) refers to a clinically heterogeneous group of rare Mendelian diseases that affect adipose tissue. To date, six subtypes have been related to genes, including *LMNA* (MIM:#151660) [1], *PPARG* (MIM: #604367) [2,3], *AKT2* [4], *CIDEA* (MIM: #615238) [5], *PLIN1* (MIM: #613877) [6], and *LIPF* (MIM: #615980) [7]. A seventh subtype, the Köbberling syndrome, or type 1 FPLD (FPLD1; MIM: #608600) [8], has not been related to a gene, but it was proposed to exhibit an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern.

The classical phenotypical type 2 FPLD, or Dunnigan disease [9], is generally linked to mutations in exon 8 of the *LMNA* gene. The disease starts in women at puberty, and it is mostly characterized by the loss of adipose tissue in the lower limbs and buttocks and, to a minor extent, in the abdominal subcutaneous fat depots. In addition, it is associated with fat accumulations in the face, neck, axillae, labia major, and visceral adipose tissue. Moreover, these patients have well-defined muscles, including gastrocnemius hypertrophy, flebomegaly, and acanthosis nigricans. This lipodystrophic phenotype is common to all the other FPLD subtypes, with some variations related to the fat accumulation sites [2-8]. Due the particular abnormal fat distribution, men are difficult to diagnose [10,11]. Subjects with FPLD develop early insulin resistance [12], and they show a propensity for developing diabetes mellitus, hypertriglyceridaemia, and hepatic steatosis [13]. As a consequence of these factors, patients with FPLD have an elevated risk of cardiovascular diseases, particularly women [14,15]. The phenotype of FPLD also includes a high frequency of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and various fertility problems [16,17].

Köbberling syndrome is clinically characterized by a loss of adipose tissue in the buttocks and limbs, which generally starts in childhood. This fat loss is associated with an accumulation of fat in the trunk, particularly subcutaneous and visceral abdominal fat, and occasionally, fat accumulations in the face and neck (Figure 1). Patients develop insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus, and

1 hypertriglyceridaemia. The eponym derives from the original reports published by M.G. Dunnigan
2 and J. Köbberling in 1974 [18], 1975 [19], and 1986 [20]. In the first reports [18,19], the authors
3 considered this partial lipodystrophy an autosomal dominant disease; however, in the later report [20],
4 it was postulated to have an X-linked dominance pattern with lethality in the hemizygous male. Later,
5 in 1997, S.N.J. Jackson et al. [21], questioned the assumed pattern of inheritance after studying a 23-
6 member pedigree diagnosed with Köbberling-Dunnigan syndrome, and they postulated an autosomal
7 dominant inheritance. It must be emphasized that there is a possibility that, based on the phenotype
8 descriptions of the patients in that pedigree [21], some might have been carriers of *LMNA* gene
9 mutations that had not been discovered until three years later [1].

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11 The Köbberling syndrome has been considered an independent clinical entity. However, only one
12 study, published twelve years ago by K.L. Herbst et al. [8], thoroughly described the clinical and
13 anthropometric features of 13 women diagnosed with Köbberling syndrome. That was the first study
14 to exclude *LMNA* and *PPARG* mutations, and the main clinical characteristics were a paucity of fat in
15 the limbs, childhood onset, central obesity, insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus, and
16 hypertriglyceridaemia. Oddly, only 38% of those patients stated that they had relatives with a similar
17 phenotype.

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19 In the present study, we evaluated the family history, clinical features, anthropometric features, body
20 composition, and plasma biochemistry in a large cohort of 98 women diagnosed with FPLD1, after
21 ruling out mutations in *LMNA*, *PPARG* and *LIPE* genes. We aimed to establish clear diagnostic
22 criteria for FPLD1 and determine the probable inheritance pattern.

23 **SUBJECTS AND METHODS**

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25 This study was approved by the Ethics Review Panel of the Consellería de Sanidade, Xunta de
26 Galicia, Spain. The study was carried out according to the ethical guidelines described in the
27 Declaration of Helsinki. All subjects provided informed consent for participation in the study and for
28 the publication of their clinical, biochemical, and genetic information.

1 The study was conducted at the Division of Endocrinology and Nutrition in the University Clinical
2 Hospital of Santiago de Compostela (Spain). The cohort included 98 women with FPLD1 (Köbberling
3 group, FPLD1) that had visited the clinic to consult for diabetes mellitus, obesity, and/or
4 dyslipidaemia. Type 1 FPLD was suspected during a visual exam, based on a lack of fat in the lower
5 extremities and buttocks and fat accumulation in the abdomen. A control group included 60 women
6 without the Köbberling phenotype that had consulted for type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, and/or
7 dyslipidaemia, or were recruited from the hospital staff. Exclusion criteria were the presence of
8 Dunnigan disease; type 3 FPLD; Cushing syndrome; glucocorticoid consumption; nephrotic
9 syndrome; advanced cardiac, renal, or liver disease; or advanced cancer. Twenty-five women with a
10 molecular diagnosis of Dunnigan disease were also included in this study (Dunnigan group, FPLD2).

11 All subjects provided an exhaustive clinical history and underwent a physical exam. Particular
12 attention was directed to the lipodystrophic phenotype onset; metabolic, pancreatic, hepatic, and
13 cardiac complications; and obstetric history. To assess the genetic origin of FPLD1, we investigated
14 whether other individuals in the family were affected by meeting with relatives or, when not possible,
15 asking patients to describe relatives or supply photos of relatives (Figure 2).

16 Height and body weight were measured with a stadiometer and a digital balance, respectively. A
17 flexible tape was used to measure the waist (while standing, the smallest horizontal circumference
18 between the ribs and the iliac crest) and the hips (while standing, the maximum circumference around
19 the buttocks). Skinfolds were measured in triplicate at the triceps, biceps, subscapular, suprailiac,
20 thigh, and calf sites. All skinfold sites were measured on the dominant extremity with a Lange
21 skinfold calliper (Cambridge Scientific Industries, Maryland, USA). The segmental body distribution
22 of fat, including abdominal visceral fat [22], was assessed by whole-body dual-energy X-ray
23 absorptiometry (DEXA) with a Lunar model DPX apparatus (GE Medical Systems, Pittsburgh, PA,
24 USA). **Several truncal:limbs ratios were calculated as follow: SSc/Calf SF = subscapular
25 skinfold/calf skinfold; T/LL Fat Kg = Truncal/Lower limbs fat in kilograms; T/LL Fat % =
26 Truncal/Lower limbs fat in percentage.**

***LMNA, PPARG and LIPE* mutation analysis**

DNA was prepared from peripheral white blood cells with standard procedures [23]. DNA from the Köbberling group was amplified with PCR to investigate *LMNA* exons 1-12, *PPARG* exons 1-8, *LIPE* exon 1-10 and the surrounding intronic sequences. The PCR products were purified with Illustra ExoStar 1-step (Ge Healthcare, Freiburg, Germany), then directly sequenced with the same primers used for amplification. Sequencing was performed with the BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (PE Applied Biosystems, CA, USA). Electropherograms were produced with an ABI 3100 Automated Sequencing Analyzer (PE Applied Biosystems, CA, USA) and analysed with Sequence Navigator software (PE Applied Biosystems, CA, USA).

Biochemistry

Fasting serum samples were analysed for glucose, triglycerides, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-c), high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-c), leptin, and insulin, as described previously [12]. Blood haemoglobin A1c was measured with ion-exchange high-performance liquid chromatography (Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc., Hercules, CA, USA). Alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase (AST), and gamma-glutamyltransferase were determined with enzymatic methods on an ADVIA analyser (Siemens, Bayer Diagnostics, Tarrytown, NY, USA). In subjects that did not require insulin treatment, insulin resistance was evaluated with the HOMA method [24]. Cushing's syndrome was ruled out in all patients by measuring urinary free cortisol or by administering a suppression test with 1 mg of dexamethasone.

Statistical analysis

Data are expressed as the means \pm standard deviations (SD). For each continuous variable, the assumption of a normal distribution was tested with the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. The X² test was used to compare qualitative variables. The means of variables with normal distributions were compared with the ANOVA and Student t test for independent samples. The means of non-normally distributed, independent variables were compared with the Kruskal-Wallis and Mann–Whitney tests. Post-hoc analyses were performed with the Bonferroni test. **The screening ability of various**

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truncal:lower limbs ratios to identify individuals with FPLD1 was explored using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. The area under of the ROC curves (AUC) was used to determine which ratio showed the highest accuracy for FPLD1 screening. An AUC higher than 0.8 corresponds to a excellent discrimination [25]. An optimal cut-off point for each ratio was defined as that with a sensitivity higher than 0.8 and 1-specificity lower than 0.2. The best cut-off point was selected as that with a highest Youden's index [26]. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyses were carried out with SPSS 22.0 (Chicago, Illinois; USA).

RESULTS

The Köbberling group displayed no pathogenetic mutations in the *LMNA*, *PPARG* or *LIPE* genes. Anthropometric features and body composition data are shown in Table 1. The waist-to-hip ratio and subscapular skinfolds were significantly higher in the Köbberling group than in the control and Dunnigan groups. In contrast, skinfolds of the biceps, triceps, thigh, and calf were significantly lower in the Dunnigan group than in the Köbberling group; and they were lower in the Köbberling group than in the controls.

Based on the DEXA studies, fat contents in the total body, in the subcutaneous abdominal region, and in the upper limbs were similar between FPLD1 (n=85) and controls. However, in the FPLD1 group, fat contents were markedly reduced in the lower limbs and increased in the visceral adipose depots (Table 1). In the Dunnigan group, fat content was significantly reduced in all evaluated areas compared to the other groups, except in the visceral depot, where the fat content was similar to that observed in controls (Table 1).

The frequencies of acanthosis nigricans, acrochordons, and hirsutism were significantly greater in the FPLD1 group than in controls (acanthosis, controls:13.5% vs FPLD1:46.3%, $p < 0.001$; acrochordons, controls:2.0% vs FPLD1:31.9%, $p < 0.001$; hirsutism, controls: 3.7% vs FPLD1:18.8%, $p < 0.009$). Disturbances in glucose metabolism, and blood pressure levels (glucose levels disturbances: 30% vs 80.6%, $p < 0.0001$; HBP:48.3% vs 68.4%, $p < 0.0001$) also occurred more frequently in the FPLD1 group than in controls. Moreover, the FPLD1 group had a higher prevalence of macrovascular complications

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than controls. However, the prevalence of microvascular complications was similar among groups (Table 1).

The prevalences of hypertriglyceridaemia and hepatic steatosis (assessed by ultrasonography) were clearly different among groups. Hypertriglyceridaemia and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) were observed in 66.3% and 77.6%, respectively, of patients with Köbberling compared to 15% and 25.7%, respectively, of control patients ($p < 0.0001$).

Analyses of the biochemical data showed that fasting glucose levels were higher in the FPLD1 group than in the control and FPLD2 groups (Table 1). Similar results were obtained with haemoglobin A1c, the HOMA index, triglycerides, and gamma-glutamyltransferase concentrations. These levels were always higher in the Köbberling group than in controls, but they were not statistically significantly different when compared to levels in the Dunnigan group (Table 1). No differences in leptin, ALT, or AST levels were found between the FPLD1 and control groups, but plasma insulin was higher in subjects with lipodystrophy than in controls.

The gynaecological history showed significant differences in the frequencies of gestational diabetes and oligomenorrhea. Both conditions were more prevalent in the FPLD1 group than the control group (70.9% vs 9%, $p < 0.001$; 32.6% vs 15.4%, $p < 0.025$). However, the groups were not different in the numbers of miscarriages, history of infertility, and incidence of PCOS (Table 1). Newborns of mothers with FPLD1 had an average weight of 4315 ± 392 g, significantly higher than the weights of newborns of mothers that had diabetes, but not FPLD1 (3379 ± 300 g) (data not published). There were no differences in cancer prevalence among groups.

The results of comparing control and Köbberling groups after excluding women with diabetes were similar to those that include diabetic women (Table 2). So, the skinfolds from extremities were lower in Köbberling group, and the same was true for lower limb fat with a higher fat accumulation in abdominal visceral depots. Non diabetic Köbberling patients showed a higher glucose levels, A1c percentage, plasma triglycerides concentration and insulin levels than non diabetic control subjects.

1 Also these FPLD1 women showed a worse insulin sensitivity and a higher percentage of obstetric
2 complications and PCOS.
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5 Patients with Köbberling syndrome were asked when they started to show a distinguishable pattern of
6 body fat distribution, and when possible, with graphic documentation. The responses showed that the
7 phenotype onset mostly occurred in childhood (56%), sometimes between puberty and youth (31%),
8 and infrequently in menopause (13%). Familial information was not accessible in 8 cases, because
9 they were adopted or raised in a single-parent family. Of the remaining 90 pedigrees, at least 78
10 (87%) possessed first-degree relatives with Köbberling syndrome. In 49 cases, we acquired sufficient
11 data to perform a family tree that extended across nearly three generations. Among these, the pattern
12 of inheritance was autosomal recessive in 7 pedigrees (14%), and autosomal dominant in 42 pedigrees
13 (86%).
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26 **Köbberling classification by tertiles of the percentage of fat in the lower limbs**

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29 Next, we aimed to establish a cut-off value for the lack of lower-extremity fat in patients with FPLD1
30 that could be associated with the risk of complications. Patients with FPLD1 were divided into
31 tertiles, according to the percentage of lower-limb fat, as follows: tertile 1: $\leq 30.8\%$ (T1K); tertile 2:
32 30.8-36.7% (T2K); and tertile 3: $>36.7\%$ (T3K). The results are shown in Table 3.
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39 The three tertiles showed no significant differences in BMI or WHR. On the other hand, T2K and
40 T3K, which had higher percentages of lower-limb fat than T1K, also had higher percentages of total,
41 upper-limb, and truncal fat, than T1K (Table 3). Haemoglobin A1c and HOMA values significantly
42 increased as the percentage of lower-limb fat decreased. Moreover, patients in T1K were at higher risk
43 of diabetes and microvascular complications than patients in T3K. No significant differences among
44 tertiles were found in hirsutism, oligomenorrhea, gestational diabetes, miscarriage history, NAFLD,
45 lipodystrophy onset, or macrovascular complications of diabetes. Moreover, no differences among
46 tertiles were found in the number of affected relatives, the inheritance pattern, or the age of
47 lipodystrophy onset.
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1 Patients in the T1K and T3K groups were compared with controls and patients with Dunnigan
2 disease. As expected, the waist-to-hip ratio was significantly higher in the FPLD1 group. Also,
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4 skinfolds were significantly lower in the Dunnigan group than in T1K and T3K. However, no
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6 significant difference was found in the thigh and calf skinfolds between the Dunnigan group and the
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8 T1K group. The triceps skinfolds were lower in T1K than in controls, but not in T3K compared to
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10 controls.

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14 Glucose disturbances were significantly worse in the T1K group, even compared to those of the
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16 Dunnigan group (96.4% vs 72.0%, $p < 0.05$). However, glucose disturbances were not significantly
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18 different between T3K and controls.
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21 **ROC curves analysis**

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24 **The results of ROC curves analyses are shown in Figure 3 and Table 4. Based on the AUC, all of**
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26 **three ratios showed excellent discrimination capacity (AUC higher than 0.8), but the best results**
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28 **corresponded to SSc/Calf skinfolds, herein after named KöB index. The optimal cut-off for this**
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30 **ratio was 3.477 (sensitivity: 89%, specificity: 84%). T/LL Fat Kg ratio also showed an excellent**
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32 **ROC curve analysis, with an optimal cut-off value of 2.153 (sensitivity: 89%, specificity: 78%).**
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34 **More than 80% (82.6%) of women with T/LL Fat Kg higher than 2.153 had impaired glucose**
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36 **metabolism (72% of them were diabetic), in comparison to 23% with impaired glucose**
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38 **metabolism in those with T/LL Fat Kg lower than the cut-off point ($p < 0.0001$). Using the KöB**
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40 **index, the percentage of women with impaired glucose metabolism was 78% in those who were**
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42 **above the cut-off point vs. 40% in women who were below that value ($p < 0.0001$).**
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47 **DISCUSSION**

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51 This study shows that a clinical visual inspection was sufficiently accurate for identifying women
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53 with low percentages of fat in the lower extremities, even when they were more obese than controls.
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55 Thus, Köbberling syndrome represents a particular subtype of lipodystrophy, in which women have
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57 difficulty storing surplus energy in the hips and lower limbs, and this feature became more evident
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59 during menopause (see supplementary information). The lack of subcutaneous fat plus the
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1 accumulation of central adipose tissue increased the risk of developing metabolic, cardiac, and
2 gynaecological complications. On the other hand, identifying the mechanisms responsible for this
3 particular fat distribution was out of the scope of this study. Likewise, our results clearly showed that
4 the abnormal fat distribution phenotype appeared early (in childhood) in a high percentage of cases,
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6 consistent with findings in other studies [8].
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11 As a group, patients with FPLD1 had worse lipid parameters, more severe insulin resistance, and a
12 higher risk of impaired glucose metabolism than control patients. Moreover, when patients with
13 FPLD1 were compared to patients with the classical Dunnigan disease, despite the fact that the latter
14 patients had more severe lipodystrophy, the former patients clearly had a worse metabolic profile.
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16 This could be due to the fact that the women with Dunnigan disease were younger, thinner, and had a
17 lower percentage of visceral fat than women with FPLD1. These data supported the notion that, at
18 least in FPLD1, the excess visceral adiposity and the inability to store surplus energy in peripheral
19 depots contributed to insulin resistance and its metabolic and cardiovascular consequences.
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30 The association between lower-limb fat content and metabolic disorders became clear when we
31 divided our cohort into tertiles according to the percentage of fat in the lower limbs. Women in the
32 first tertile ($\leq 30.8\%$ of fat in lower limbs) had worse metabolic profiles and HOMA index than
33 women in the other tertiles, but not differences in cardiovascular complications or visceral fat. These
34 results are in agreement with other studies on obesity and body fat distribution [27, 28]. It has been
35 well established that lower-limb fat accumulation, as opposed to central obesity, is inversely
36 associated with metabolic risk factors and cardiovascular disease. In this regard, Köbberling
37 syndrome represents a singular model of the importance of lower-body fat content on the risk of
38 diabetes. The division in tertiles of lower-limb fat highlighted the importance of fat depots in
39 extremities for the risk of developing diabetes but also the relationship between cardiovascular
40 disease and abdominal visceral fat. No differences were found neither in visceral fat nor in
41 cardiovascular complications among tertiles.
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With the aim to find out a practical clinical index for FPLD1 diagnosis other than visual inspection, several truncal:lower limbs ratios were analysed by ROC curves. Although all of the three studied ratios gave rise to excellent results, with AUC around 0.9, the KöB index was the one with highest AUC and Younden's index. Although, DEXA-based ratios provide quite similar results, from a clinical practical point of view an skinfold-based ratio as KöB index is harmless, faster, and cheaper.

We investigated the aetiology, because the inheritance pattern of Köbberling disease is controversial. Previous studies have produced conflicting results, partly due to the difficulty in identifying affected men, and partly because the most clear phenotype was observed in obese, menopausal women. In other words, it is difficult to identify the adipose phenotype in non-obese, young women (see supplementary information). Most of the patients in the present study showed a Mendelian inheritance pattern (86% autosomal dominant). This suggested that a particular gene was involved in the aetiology. To date, six genes have been related to FPLD [1-7] and they have given rise to non-allelic, allelic, and phenotypic heterogeneity. Although the majority of these genes encode proteins clearly involved in adipogenesis (*PPARG*), lipogenesis (*LIPE*, *AKT2*), or lipid droplet synthesis (*CIDEA*, *PLIN1*), *LMNA* was unique, because it did not, initially, appear to play a role in these processes. Consequently, many candidate genes could contribute to that particular phenotype. However, given the broad adipose spectrum observed in FPLD1 patients, oligogenic inheritance cannot be ruled out.

This study has some limitations which would have to be taking into account. First of all, we do not have sequenced all of the FPLD-related genes. Although this could mean to have lost some specific FPLD diagnosis, we believe that this was not the case. So, people with mutations in *PLIN1* or *CIDEA* has not been reported of having fat accumulation at all [5,6]. In addition, in type 4 FPLD patients has not fat also in upper-extremities [6]. Other important question is that we did not find a bimodal distribution in the lower-limb fat clearly expressing a differentiated adipose phenotype. On the other hand, the fact that a majority of these patients reported to have relatives with similar phenotype is very suggestive of that Köbberling syndrome is a Mendelian disease. **Taking together these two**

1 assertions it is reasonable to raise that FPLD1 is a singular disorder due to mutations in one or more
2 individual genes plus several environmental modifiers.
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5 In summary, we found that Köbberling syndrome was mostly inherited in an autosomal dominant
6 pattern, and typically showed a paediatric onset. The phenotype was most prominent when the patient
7 gained weight, and it worsened during menopause. The metabolic disease in the Köbberling syndrome
8 is a function of increased visceral fat combined with decreased lower extremity subcutaneous fat. **A**
9 **value of KöB index higher than 3.477 is highly suggestive of this syndrome.** With these findings in
10 mind, we recommend encouraging young first-degree relatives of these patients to follow a healthy
11 life style, and they should be warned that they have a higher risk of complications than general
12 population.
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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Panels A and B: A typical patient with Köbberling syndrome characterized by fat loss in the lower limbs, with excessive fat accumulation in the trunk,. Panel C: Another FPLD1 patient with the characteristic phenotype: truncal fat accumulation and lack of fat in buttocks and lower limbs. Panel D: Well-defined muscles in the lower limbs in another patient with Köbberling syndrome.

Figure 2. Two pedigrees of patients with Köbberling syndrome. Panels A-D: Genealogical tree (A) that shows 4 affected members, all of them with diabetes mellitus and hypertriglyceridemia. Two sisters are showed (panels B and C), corresponding to patients II.3 and II.4. Panel D: acanthosis nigricans and acrochordons in patient II.4 Panels E-G: Genealogical tree (A) that shows 4 affected members from three generations, all of them with diabetes mellitus and hypertriglyceridemia. Panels F and G shown patients I.1 and II.3 with the classical Köbberling phenotype.

Figure 3. ROC curves for each truncal:lower limbs ratios for the diagnosis of Köberling syndrome. SSc/Calf SF: Subscapular/Calf skinfolds; T/LL Fat kg: Truncal/Lower Limbs fat in Kg; T/LL Fat %: Truncal/Lower Limbs fat in percentage.

TABLE 1. Demographic, anthropometric, biochemical, and clinical features of the studied subjects.

	CONTROL (n=60)	KÖBBERLING (n=98)	DUNNIGAN (n=25)
Age (years)	48.8±14.2	52.5±11.5	40.7±16.1
Menopausal status (%)	53	59	28 ^{†*}
BMI (kg/m ²)	32.1±8.2	34.6±4.7*	24.6±3.4 ^{†*}
WHR	0.86±0.1	1.02±0.1*	0.92±0.29 ^{†*}
Triceps SF (mm)	35.0±12.1	26.4±11.4*	6.2±4.3 ^{†*}
Biceps SF (mm)	27.2±12.4	21.9±10.7*	5.2±3.3 ^{†*}
Subscapular SF (mm)	36.2±15.2	42.2±11.6*	22.9±11.9 ^{†*}
Suprailiac SF (mm)	42.9±17.6	41.8±14.1	13.1±9.6 ^{†*}
Thigh SF (mm)	37.2±16.5	20.5±10.7*	5.5±5.4 ^{†*}
Calf SF (mm)	20.2±12.7	6.3±4.4*	3.6±1.6 ^{†*}
Total fat (%)	43.1±8.3	43.0±4.5	25.7±5.5 ^{†*}
Total fat (kg)	35.2±13.6	34.5±7.4	17.4±6.3 ^{†*}
Total fat free mass (Kg)	41.5±5.9	43.3±9.0	47.0±6.1 [*]
Upper limbs fat (%)	43.9±7.4	43.1±4.9	23.3±6.1 ^{†*}
Upper limbs fat (kg)	3.8±1.0	3.7±1.3	1.7±0.8 ^{†*}
Upper limbs fat free mass (Kg)	4.3±0.8	4.8±1.0 [*]	5.3±1.4 [*]
Lower limbs fat (%)	42.2±6.3	33.3±6.2*	18.2±4.7 ^{†*}
Lower limbs fat kg)	11.1±3.9	7.4±2.2*	3.4±1.5 ^{†*}
Lower limbs fat free mass (Kg)	14.0±2.5	13.7±2.8	14.4±3.2
Trunk fat (%)	45.4±11.2	49.4±5.0*	30.8±7.1 ^{†*}
Trunk fat (kg)	19.5±9.4	22.5±5.4*	11.1±4.4 ^{†*}
Trunk fat free mass (Kg)	20.0±4.0	21.9±3.9 [*]	11.1±4.4 ^{†*}
Visceral fat (g)	1434±886	2374±909*	1173±596 [†]
Basal glucose (mmol/L)	5.7±1.8	8.9±4.7*	7.8±3.9 ^{†*}
Hb A1c (%) (mmol/mol)	5.9±1.2 (41)	7.6±1.9 (59.6)*	6.8±2.1 (50.8) [*]
Plasma Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.1±0.4	2.4±1.7*	1.8±1.1 [*]
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.4±0.4	1.1±0.4*	1.1±0.5 [*]
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	3.2±1.2	3.1±0.8	2.9±0.9 [†]
Plasma leptin (µg/L)	23±16	21±16	4±5 ^{†**†}
Plasma insulin (mIU/l)	11±7	23±32*	19±11 [*]
AST (IU/L)	19±9	23±17	17±8
ALT (IU/L)	26±14	34±30	23±12
GGT (UI/L)	19±14	31±39*	26±22
HOMA	2.6±2.0	7.5±2.1*	5.1±4.3 [*]
Impaired Glucose Metabolism (%)	30	81*	72 ^{†*}
Cardiovascular complications	7	18*	8
Hypertriglyceridemia (%)	15	66*	64 [*]
PCOS and obstetric complications (%)	18	54*	20
Autosomal dominant inheritance (%)	NA	86	100 [†]
Lipodystrophy onset (%)	NA	Childhood (56) Puberty (12) Youth (19)	Childhood (4) [†] Puberty (96) [†]

Data are reported as the mean±SD or %. *: p<0.05 vs. control; †: p<0.05 vs. the Köbberling group. “Impaired glucose metabolism” includes impaired basal glucose, glucose intolerance, and diabetes mellitus; “Obstetric complications” includes miscarriages, gestational diabetes, and/or macrosomy. WHR: waist-to-hip ratio; SF: skinfold; PCOS: polycystic ovarian syndrome; NA: not applicable

TABLE 2. Demographic, anthropometric, biochemical, and clinical features of the non-diabetic subjects.

	CONTROL (n=44)	KÖBBERLING (n=28)
Age (years)	44.1±12.4	46.8±11.6
Menopausal status (%)	60	64
BMI (kg/m ²)	30.8±8.38	33.3±5.1
WHR	0.83±0.1	1.01±0.07*
Triceps SF (mm)	35.8±12.6	27.7±11.5*
Biceps SF (mm)	28±12.4	23.3±12.2
Subscapular SF (mm)	34.9±14.5	41.7±12.0
Suprailiac SF (mm)	40.7±16.2	39.8±12.4
Thigh SF (mm)	38.7±18.3	23.2±9.8*
Calf SF (mm)	21.3±13.7	8.0±4.7*
Total fat (%)	42.2±8.3	43.7±4.22
Total fat (kg)	33.4±13.4	35.1±7.0
Total fat free mass (Kg)	41.2±6.7	42.8±4.0
Upper limbs fat (%)	43.1±7.7	43.5±4.4
Upper limbs fat (kg)	3.7±1.3	3.8±0.9
Upper limbs fat free mass (Kg)	4.4±0.8	4.7±0.8
Lower limbs fat (%)	42.4±6.4	35.9±5.0*
Lower limbs fat (kg)	11.3±4.1	8.3±1.9*
Lower limbs fat free mass (Kg)	14.0±2.7	13.4±2.7
Trunk fat (%)	43.8±11.1	50.1±5.0*
Trunk fat (kg)	17.5±8.8	22.7±5.5*
Trunk fat free mass (Kg)	20.3±3.7	20.1±2.0
Visceral fat (g)	1249.9±790.7	1887.8±670.0*
Basal glucose (mmol/L)	86±9	95±17*
Hb A1c (%) (mmol/mol)	5.3±0.3	5.8±0.8*
Plasma Triglycerides (mmol/L)	89±31	152±78*
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	55±14	45±14*
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	129±28	139±33
Plasma leptin (µg/L)	21±16	23±18
Plasma insulin (mIU/l)	8.7±5.5	16.0±11.3*
AST (IU/L)	17±6	20±21
ALT (IU/L)	24±11	34±46
GGT (UI/L)	14±8	31±34*
HOMA	2±1.3	4±3.7*
Cardiovascular complications	0	0
Hypertriglyceridemia (%)	4	50*
PCOS and obstetric complications (%)	7	54.5*
Autosomal dominant inheritance (%)	NA	90
Lipodystrophy onset (%)	NA	Childhood (50) Puberty (23) Youth (19)

Data are reported as the mean±SD or %. *: p<0.05 vs. control. “Obstetric complications” includes miscarriages, gestational diabetes, and/or macrosomy. WHR: waist-to-hip ratio; SF: skinfold; PCOS: polycystic ovarian syndrome; NA: not applicable

TABLE 3. Demographic, anthropometric, biochemical, and clinical features of patients with Köbberling syndrome, grouped according to tertiles (T1K, T2K, or T3K) of the percentage of fat in the lower limbs.

	T1K (n=28)	T2K (n=28)	T3K (n=29)
Lower limbs fat (%)	≤30.8	30.8-36.7	>36.7
Age (y.)	55.8±9.0	53.7±10.4	50.43±11.0
Menopausal status (%)	75	66	50
BMI (kg/m ²)	33.98±3.98	34.50±4.09	35.93±5.16
WHR	1.06±0.08	1.02±0.04	1.02±0.05
Triceps SF (mm)	24.90±13.58	24.82±9.98	28.21±10.62
Biceps SF (mm)	23.94±10.94	19.67±10.74	21.35±9.80
Suprailiac SF (mm)	44.26±13.55	41.77±17.31	37.85±9.80
Subscapular SF (mm)	43.95±8.72	39.04±13.61	45.96±11.05
Thigh SF (mm)	11.06±5.36	18.29±8.61*	28.14±10.08*†
Calf SF (mm)	3.84±1.50	5.16±3.43	9.21±5.10*†
Total fat (%)	40.14±4.52	42.65±3.37*	46.24±3.21*†
Total fat (kg)	32.17±7.49	33.90±6.77	38.18±6.62*
Total fat free mass (Kg)	44.5±10.4	40.4±10.3	41.9±4.8
Upper limbs fat (%)	41.26±5.74	42.87±4.42	45.49±3.85*
Upper limbs fat (kg)	3.73±0.98	3.93±0.91	4.01±1.11
Upper limbs free fat mass (Kg)	5.0±1.5	4.9±0.7	4.5±0.7†
Lower limbs fat (%)	26.15±3.62	33.92±1.69*	39.77±2.18*†
Lower limbs fat (kg)	5.36±1.60	7.55±1.06*	9.23±1.85*†
Lower limbs free fat mass (Kg)	14.1±3.2	13.9±2.0	13.1±3.0
Trunk fat (%)	47.29±4.88	48.99±4.82	51.90±4.23*
Trunk fat (kg)	22.12±5.61	22.04±5.17	23.97±5.03
Trunk free fat mass (Kg)	21.6±5.8	21.8±2.5	20.4±4.7
Visceral fat (gr)	2548±1083	2315±851	2256±781
Basal glucose (mmol/L)	10.21±4.4	7.7±3.1	8.1±3.9
Hb A1c (%)(mmol/ml)	8.5±1.7 (69.4)	7.5±1.8 (58.5)	6.7±1.2 (49.7)*
Plasma Triglycerides (mmol/L)	2.8±0.8	2.2±1.2	1.9±1.2

HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.1±0.3	1.2±0.4	1.2±0.4
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.8±1.1	3.2±0.9	3.2±1.2
Plasma leptin (µg/L)	24±16	18±16	28±18
Plasma insulin (mIU/l)	27±18	19±18	18±21
AST (IU/L)	24±14	28±18	16±6.0
ALT (IU/L)	30±12	39±23	28±18
GGT (UI/L)	29±24	48±48	32±32
HOMA	12.1±9.7	6.0±5.3*	4.3*
Impaired glucose metabolism (%)	96.43	86.21	67.86*
Cardiovascular complications (%)	28.6	27.2	10.7
Microvascular complications (%)	60.7	20.7*	21.4*
Hypertriglyceridemia (%)	75.0	65.5	57.14
PCOS and obstetric complications (%)	72.0	50.0	55.5

Data are reported as the mean±SD or %. T1K: tertile 1: ≤30.8% lower-limb fat; T2K: tertile 2: 30.8-36.7% lower-limb fat; T3K: tertile 3: >36.7% lower-limb fat; *: p<0.05 vs. T1K; †: p<0.05 vs. T2K; “Impaired glucose metabolism” includes impaired basal glucose, glucose intolerance, and diabetes mellitus; “Obstetric complications” includes miscarriages, gestational diabetes, and/or macrosomy. F: fertile; M: menopausal; WHR: waist-to-hip ratio; SF: skinfold; PCOS: polycystic ovarian syndrome

Table 4. ROC curve analysis for different truncal:lower limbs ratios

Trucal/Lower Limbs	Cut-off	Sen.(%)	Spe.(%)	AUC (95% CI)	Youden Index	PPV	NPV
SSc/Calf SF	3.477	89	84	0.933 (0.89-0.98)	0.724	0.87	0.83
T/LL Fat kg	2.153	89	78	0.918 (0.86-0.97)	0.671	0.84	0.87
T/LL Fat %	1.282	81	87	0.911 (0.86-0.97)	0.676	0.89	0.83

SSc/Calf SF: Subscapular/Calf skinfolds; T/LL Fat kg: Truncal/Lower Limbs fat in Kg; T/LL Fat %: Truncal/Lower Limbs fat in percentage; Sen.: sensitivity; Spe.: Specificity; AUC: area under curve; PPV: Positive Predictive Value; NPV: Negative Predictive Value.